

Development of a Monte Carlo-Based Burnup Model and Reconfiguration of the TRIGA Mark II Reactor at LENA

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ABSTRACT

A detailed Monte Carlo model of the TRIGA Mark II research reactor, at the Laboratorio Energia Nucleare Applicata (LENA) of the University of Pavia, was developed using the Serpent2 code to study the reactor behavior under fuel ageing effects and to support core optimization. The model reproduces the geometry, material composition, and operational history of the reactor, allowing a fully coupled simulation of neutron transport and fuel burnup. A long-term evolution of the core from 1965 to 2025 was computed to estimate the isotopic composition and reactivity changes. The results were validated against experimental data and previous MCNP-based simulations coupled with a custom burnup solver. Good agreement was found for the evolution of uranium isotopes, reactivity trends, and control rod calibration data, confirming the reliability of the Serpent model. The validated model was then used to design a new core configuration aimed at restoring reactivity without introducing new fuel elements. This work highlights the validity and potential of Monte Carlo methods, and in particular Serpent2, as accurate and versatile tools for research reactor analysis, enabling consistent prediction of fuel evolution, reactivity behavior, and safe optimization of core configurations.

Keywords: Depletion calculations, Monte Carlo codes, Serpent, TRIGA Mark II reactor, Reconfiguration

1. INTRODUCTION

The TRIGA Mark II reactor, operating since 1965 at the Laboratorio Energia Nucleare Applicata (LENA) of the University of Pavia, is a pool-type research reactor with a nominal power of 250 kW. Over the decades, it has been employed in a wide range of research activities, exploiting its high neutron flux (up to $2 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at full power).

The reactor core consists of a circular lattice with 90 positions arranged in five concentric rings with rotational symmetry. Special positions are occupied by three control rods (CRs), irradiation channels, and the neutron source, allowing a maximum of 85 fuel elements (FEs). The remaining positions are filled with graphite dummy elements. Core locations are denoted by a letter (ring B-F) and a number specifying the location within the ring.

Each fuel element is composed of a mixture of zirconium hydride, acting as moderator, and uranium (8% wt, enriched to nearly 20%). Over the years, General Atomics manufactured different FE types, varying in Zr-H ratio, burnable poison content, and cladding material. The original FEs had aluminium cladding, while later ones adopted stainless steel, more resistant to thermo-mechanical stress but less transparent to neutrons.

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The core has been extensively studied through both experimental measurements [1, 2, 3, 4] and numerical analyses. An MCNP5-based [5] model was developed to assess the reactor's neutronic behaviour [6, 7], coupled with thermo-hydraulic simulations [8] for fuel temperature distribution and an custom code for fuel burnup evaluation over the period 1965–2013 [9]. These tools showed good agreement with benchmark experiments.

More recently, a Serpent [10] Monte Carlo model was developed, allowing a coupled evaluation of neutronics, burnup, and thermo-hydraulic effects within a flexible geometry. Validated against experimental data for the first critical configuration [11], the model reproduced results obtained with MCNP. This paper presents the development of a new core configuration using Serpent (v2.1.31) aimed at increasing reactivity and extending operational lifetime. A dedicated burnup simulation was performed to reproduce reactor conditions after decades of operation.

Section 2 discusses fuel evolution and its impact on reactivity. Section 3 describes the Serpent-based burnup calculation over 1965–2025. Section 4 presents results and validation of the burnup model. Section 5 reports the design of the new configuration, which will be adopted from January 2026.

Figure 1. Core configuration in 1965. Fuel rods are represented in green, graphite rods in yellow, control rods in red, irradiation channels in gray, and an empty channel in blue. CC = central irradiation channel (central thimble).

2. FUEL EVOLUTION AND REACTIVITY LOSS

The fission chain reaction within the reactor leads to the depletion of fissile nuclides, accumulation of neutron poisons, and production of new fissile isotopes through breeding. In the TRIGA Mark II, the reaction is mainly driven by ^{235}U fission. Its depletion, and the buildup of poisons, determines in a net reactivity loss, although ^{239}Pu is bred. This is usually compensated by withdrawing control rods, but under the effect of strong ^{135}Xe accumulation and negative thermal feedback, achieving criticality may become impossible if the core excess (CE, the core reactivity without CR insertion), is too low.

When such a condition occurs, a new core configuration must then be designed to increase the CE. An accurate reactor model is therefore crucial both for configuration design and reactivity assessment, ensuring that the system can always be safely shut down. Reliable reactivity estimation requires a detailed geometrical model and accurate isotopic compositions. The geometry model was developed in Serpent using LENA archives and General Atomics drawings, while the current fuel isotopic composition were obtained through a burnup calculation covering the entire operational history.

Fuel evolution is governed by the Bateman equations [12]:

$$\frac{dn_j}{dt} = \sum_k \gamma_j^k \Sigma^k \Phi + \sum_l \left(\lambda^{(l \rightarrow j)} + \sigma^{(l \rightarrow j)} \Phi \right) n_l - \left(\lambda^j + \sigma_a^j \Phi \right) n_j \quad (1)$$

where n_j is the concentration, λ_j the decay constant, and σ_a^j the absorption cross section of nuclide j . γ_j^k represents the fission yield of nuclide j from the fission of nuclide k , while Σ^k is the macroscopic fission cross section of the fissile nuclide k . $\lambda^{(l \rightarrow j)}$ denotes the decay rate associated with the transition $l \rightarrow j$, and $\sigma^{(l \rightarrow j)}$ is the microscopic effective cross section corresponding to that transition, induced by the neutron flux Φ . Key aspects influencing burnup calculations include:

- **Physical quantities estimation:** neutron flux and effective cross sections are derived from transport simulations using flux-weighted averages based on the computed spectrum.
- **Operating time and power:** knowledge of power history is required to integrate the Bateman equations and reproduce ON–OFF cycles for short-lived isotopes.
- **Fuel element position:** flux intensity varies with location, it is higher at the core center and affected by nearby rods or channels.
- **Axial flux distribution:** higher flux in the central axial region leads to stronger local burnup.
- **Burnup feedback:** flux distributions evolve as burnup progresses, coupling neutron transport and depletion.
- **Thermal effects:** Temperature affects cross sections and the neutron flux spectrum via Doppler broadening and zirconium hydride moderation, the latter decreasing with increasing temperature. These effects must be accounted for to obtain realistic high-power reactivity predictions.

LENA's direction provided operational records including:

- **Core configurations:** 28 documented fuel layouts and corresponding control rod positions at criticality.
- **LIVE TIME:** cumulative full-power operation time for each configuration.
- **REAL TIME:** total duration of each configuration, including shutdowns.

3. BURNUP MODEL WITH SERPENT AND CALCULATION STRATEGY

The burnup calculation require to both set up the transport simulation and the integration of the Bateman equations. The strategy adopted in the analysis presented in the paper is the following.

3.1. Bateman Equation Integration

The total simulation period was divided into discrete time steps during which flux and cross sections remain nearly constant. At each step, transport calculations are performed first, followed by the nuclide field evolution. For 1965–2013 evolution, the same strategy adopted in previous works [9] was applied, each reactor configuration corresponds to one time step, resulting in 27 steps. The *Constant Extrapolation* mode in Serpent was used to estimate flux and cross sections. It was shown in previous studies that the flux varies only slightly (less than 3%) due to burnup effects, even for the configurations with the longest operating times (up to 3600 h). Therefore, a finer time discretization is not required. Another integration method, named Predictor–Corrector, showed almost identical results when used. For the evolution from 2013 to 2025, the 28-th configuration remained unchanged, and the calculation was divided into 12 yearly steps. Fluxes and cross sections were computed for each FE, divided into five axial burnup zones, following the methodology of previous work [9], enabling comparison with earlier calculation. Daily ON/OFF cycles were not reproduced, and for each step a ON substep at 250 kW with LIVE TIME duration was simulated, followed by a OFF substep, at 1 W, to match the REAL TIME.

3.2. Neutron Transport Simulation

Serpent solves the neutron transport problem by tracking neutrons within a defined geometry, determining the neutron multiplication factor, and sampling the required physical quantities. For the fuel evolution calculations, the neutron transport simulation was configured as follows:

- 300 active cycles were simulated, each with 20,000 neutron histories.
- The nuclide cross sections were taken from the JEFF-3.1 library. The $S(\alpha, \beta)$ cross sections for thermal treatment, decay data, and fission yield data were obtained from the ENDF/B-VII library.
- High-power effects were included by assigning temperatures per depletion zone according to the values adopted in previous work [8], using Serpent's TMS (Temperature Motion Sampling) method.

4. RESULTS OF THE BURNUP CALCULATION

This section presents the results of the burnup calculation, along with a benchmark validation analysis. First, the predicted nuclide evolution is compared with that obtained from the previous model (MCNP + custom code [9]). Then, the Serpent-predicted reactivity over the last twelve years is compared with experimental measurements from low-power critical configurations, as a validation of the most recent fuel evolution. Finally, the control rod calibration procedure is described, and the Serpent predictions are compared with experimental data.

4.1. Comparison with the Previous Model

The comparison between Serpent and the previous model was performed over the period 1965–2013. Since fuel evolution reflects flux distributions, nuclide concentrations serve as indirect validation of Serpent's flux, previously benchmarked for MCNP [3]. Short-lived isotopes were excluded, as the earlier code explicitly modeled ON/OFF cycles, unlike the one developed with Serpent. The evolution of ^{235}U is presented in Figure 2. Its Bateman equations can be approximated by considering only the consumption term due to neutron absorption, providing a direct indication of the neutron flux.

Figure 2. Relative concentration of Uranium-235 evolution, averaged over the entire reactor (left), and in the five depletion volumes of FE 3455, shown together with the neutron flux (green) (right). Large variations in the flux are associated with changes in the position of the fuel element. In the right figure, thicker lines represent the average concentration in the FE, while thinner lines show the evolution within each depletion zone. Blue lines correspond to the evolution predicted by the previous model, while red lines represent the Serpent results.

While considering the evolution of ^{235}U , averaged over all the fuel elements, the fact that both codes predict nearly identical depletion of Uranium-235 (with a final relative difference in the order of 10^{-3}) serves as consistency check, since the reactor is driven by ^{235}U fission, and both models reproduce the same total ^{235}U consumption. To assess the neutron flux distribution predicted by Serpent, the evolution of ^{235}U was analysed for each fuel element and each burnup zone. The results show very good agreement between the two codes, with relative differences below 1% for every fuel element and a mean relative difference of about 0.2%. This demonstrates that both models predict similar neutron flux distributions within the reactor core. Comparing the two models revealed that, in the old code, the ^{238}U depletion was higher due to an overestimation of the effective cross section. This discrepancy was found to be related to the self-shielding effect and to the way the neutron flux energy distribution was extracted from MCNP and used in the custom code. The neutron activation measurements performed in the past did not reveal this issue, because the ^{238}U sample was placed in the water between the FEs, where the self-shielding effect is negligible, as shown in Figure 3 (left pad).

Figure 3. On the left the flux around the 6.67 eV resonance peak of ^{238}U in water (blue) and inside the fuel element (black), with a fine energy grid. On the right the Serpent predicted reactivity values for low power critical configuration over the years. The mean value and the data dispersion is represented by the black line and area.

4.2. Criticality Check

In order to validate the burnup calculation over the last twelve years of reactor operation, the system reactivity was estimated by performing a neutron transport simulation in which the control rods were positioned exactly as reported in the historical critical configurations at low power, i.e., at low temperature. Figure 3 (right pad) shows the reactivity predicted by Serpent over the years. It is evident from the data that there is a systematic deviation from the expected value of 0 \$, with an average value equal to:

$$\rho = -0.46 \pm 0.05 \text{ \$} \quad (2)$$

where the reported uncertainty corresponds to the standard deviation of the data. This corresponds to:

$$k_{\text{eff}} = 0.9966 \pm 0.0003 \quad (3)$$

as multiplication factor, which can be considered quite close to unity considering that this result is obtained after a 60-year burnup calculation, involving several approximations, and that reactivity is a highly sensitive parameter. However, it is worth noting that the reactivity trend appears to remain constant over the last 12-years, indicating that the code neither overestimates nor underestimates the fuel ageing process in the last years.

4.3. Control Rods Calibration Curves

As a further validation test, the experimental control rod calibration curves from July 2015 were reproduced using the Serpent model. The procedure consists in evaluating the reactivity insertion corresponding to a control rod extraction. The result is typically reported, for each CR position, as the cumulative reactivity gained starting from the fully inserted position. Figure 4 (left pad) shows that the Serpent prediction is in good agreement, for all three control rods, with the experimental calibration curves. This confirms the model's capability to accurately predict reactivity insertions and to correctly reproduce the neutron flux distribution, since the shape of the calibration curves is strongly dependent on the axial flux profile. This result provides an indirect validation of the computed burnup evolution, since fuel burnup was taken into account. From the control rod calibration curves, it is possible to experimentally determine the core excess. Figure 4 (right pad) shows the CE trend over the years, predicted by Serpent, is in good agreement with the experimental evaluation, further validating the burnup model.

Figure 4. On the left, the blue line shows the experimental calibration curves (uncertainty $\approx 1\%$), while the dots denote the Serpent predictions, with CR positions expressed in digits (1 digit ≈ 0.054 cm for SHIM and REG). On the right, the CE of the 28th configuration over the years is reported as the difference relative to the 27th configuration (September 2013). Dots represent Serpent results, whereas the green line shows the experimental data, with statistical uncertainty indicated by the shaded area.

5. CORE RECONFIGURATION

In 2013, low core reactivity hindered reactor operation. The reconfiguration of September 2013 increased the core excess (CE) by 0.80 ± 0.05 \$, allowing twelve additional years of operation. As reactivity again decreased by about 0.8 \$ (see Figure 4, right), a new configuration is now required. Several alternatives were evaluated via transport simulations, in order to identify the most effective intervention, starting from the current core configuration, which includes 80 FEs, with stainless-steel-clad elements in rings B and C. The viable alternatives are:

- Filling ring C with 11 aluminum-clad FEs increases CE by $0.70 \pm 0.03(stat) \pm 0.3(syst)$ \$ due to higher neutron transparency.
- Replacing two stainless-steel FEs with aluminum-clad ones (which are currently outside of the core because elongated even if within the safety parameter) adds $0.07 \pm 0.03(stat) \pm 0.3(syst)$ \$.
- Increasing the number of FE in the core raises CE by $0.22 \pm 0.03(stat) \pm 0.3(syst)$ \$ per FE. It is the last option, as it can be implemented at any time, resulting in an additional reactivity margin for the future.

The systematic error in the difference reactivity estimation is related to the configuration changes in the

Figure 5. Reactor map for the 28-th (left) and the new configuration (right). Colours are associated to FEs burnup, and the black ring represent stainless-steel cladding. Crux is associated with FEs definitely removed from the pool.

model. The new configuration was designed filling the C rings with aluminum-clad FEs, inserting two elongated bars in the E ring, while positioning the elements with the lowest burnup closer to the core center, with a symmetric distribution of the burnup to ensure a balanced core. For this configuration, the core excess was found to increase by $0.77 \pm 0.03(stat) \pm 0.3(syst)\%$, resulting an absolute value of $2.71 \pm 0.3\%$, which can be considered satisfactory. Furthermore, the control rod worths, i.e. defined as the reactivity difference between the fully inserted and fully withdrawn positions, were evaluated through the model, yielding the result in Table I.

Table I. Control rod worth for the proposed configuration estimated by Serpent.

Rod	Worth [\\$]
REG	1.4 ± 0.1
SHIM	3.4 ± 0.1
TRANS	2.3 ± 0.1

This verified that the proposed configuration satisfies the mandatory safety conditions expressed by Equations (4) and (5).

$$REG + TRANS \geq CE + 0.5\% \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(REG + TRANS + SHIM) \geq CE \quad (5)$$

6. CONCLUSIONS

Using the Monte Carlo transport code SERPENT, a new model of the TRIGA Mark II reactor at LENA was developed to simulate the reactor behavior under the effects of fuel aging. The burnup calculation was validated through several independent checks, and the model demonstrated its ability to accurately predict reactivity variations within the system. Finally, it was shown that the model can be effectively used to design a new, more reactive core configuration without the need to introduce additional fuel elements. This solution will allow the extension of the reactor's operational lifetime by at least ten years. This work highlights the validity and potential of Monte Carlo codes as powerful analytical tools for

reactor physics and core management studies.

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